

Nuts About

Leadership

A Journal of Leadership and Futures Studies

Futures and Foresight Events 2025

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“Visions make it possible to create a future that is different from the present although its seeds are in the present.”—Eleonora Barbieri Masini

The third edition of the Futures and Foresight Events calendar (2025) covers selected professional development opportunities that primarily focus on the use of futures studies and foresight in societal, technological, economic, environmental, political, and value-based (STEEPV) contexts, as well as training and learning in foresight. Only announcements that were publicly available until December 31, 2024, were used to prepare this list, which includes dates, titles, descriptions, locations, and links to the respective web pages.

A challenge during the assembly of this list was the incomplete or conflicting information found on some websites, as well as the lack of continuity in links between conference websites from one year to the next. Readers should note that events, dates, titles, and locations may change, and some events may be postponed or canceled by organizers. Therefore, they should check the specific event website not only for basic information but also to ensure that the event is legitimate. Some events may not prioritize quality, which requires attendees to double-check details, especially if the event announcements do not seem quite right; in such cases, additional verification may be necessary. Attendees should take the time to conduct thorough inspections of any conferences they wish to attend or submit papers to.

This list contains foresight and future-oriented events that are related, either directly or indirectly, to the global foresight community. It is as inclusive as possible, though not exhaustive. The events are sorted by date. All web addresses were verified at the time of publication. No liability is assumed for any errors that may have been introduced inadvertently during the assembly of this free and open-access event list. However, readers are kindly encouraged to inform the author of any mistakes or missing events in this version of the list, as an update may be released later. They may also redistribute the list freely or publish it on their websites, blogs, and social media pages, as this is how the author will receive feedback and updates.

Sincerely,

[Alireza Hejazi](#), Ph.D., M.S.F.

Editor-in-Chief, Nuts about Leadership Journal

Organizational Leadership | Strategic Foresight

Zenodo Community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/nal/>)

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Date	Title	Description	Location	Website
January				
January 6–10	Foresight Seminar	A 5-day intensive workshop in framework foresight, covering areas such as systems thinking, alternative perspectives, visioning, and planning.	Houston, TX, USA	https://dot.egr.uh.edu/programs/professional/fore/seminar
January 8	2025 Virtual Eaton Symposium	This virtual symposium brings together sci-fi community members to discuss the state of the field of speculative publishing genres.	Online	https://www.eventbrite.com/e/2025-virtual-eaton-symposium-tickets-1080463267719
January 14–16	World Future Energy Summit 2025	The summit focuses on developing plans for a sustainable future by attracting industry influencers, challengers, and advanced solution providers.	Abu Dhabi, UAE	https://www.worldfutureenergysummit.com/
January 15	20 Risks and Trends for 2025	WITA hosts the futurist Robert Moran of Brunswick Group to discuss 20 notable global trends and risks for 2025.	Online	https://www.wita.org/events/20-trends-for-2025/
January 20–24	World Economic Forum Annual Meeting	The annual meeting convenes global leaders to address key global and regional challenges.	Davos-Klosters, Switzerland	https://www.weforum.org/meetings/world-economic-forum-annual-meeting-2025/

Date	Title	Description	Location	Website
		These include responding to geopolitical shocks, stimulating growth to improve living standards, and stewarding a just and inclusive energy transition.		
January 22	Sustainability on a Shoestring Budget	This webinar offers actionable insights for organizations of any size to achieve sustainability goals with limited resources.	Online	https://www.fsmgmt.co/foresight-forum
January 23	Strategic Foresight: Leading from the Future	In this webinar, Kai Jannek and Andreas Neef will talk about how the classic world of strategy and foresight thinking can be dovetailed in practice.	Online	https://z-punkt.de/en/webinare/strategic-foresight-leading-from-the-future
January 29–30	Coastal Futures 2025: The path to 2030	This is the largest ocean conference of its kind in the UK and the 2025 edition will provide delegates with wide-ranging coverage of the critical current and future issues.	Northumberland, UK	https://coastal-futures.net/
February				
February 4–6	Urban Speculations: Cities, Technologies, Futures	This research conference may be of interest to futurists with a background in urban planning. The presenters	Lüneburg, Germany	https://logistical.city/conference/

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		will discuss speculations and anti-speculations on urban futures.		
February 10–14	Strategic Foresight for Peace and Security 2025	An online course ideal for individuals engaged in analysis and planning on peace and security issues from a government, international organization, NGO or private sector perspective.	Online	https://www.gcsp.ch/courses/strategic-foresight-peace-and-security-2025
February 11	An Introduction to Futures & Foresight	In this 60-minute webinar, Cheryl Doig will share a slice of information around the nature of futures thinking and foresight, a futures mindset, and a futures approach to inform the future.	Online	https://events.humanitix.com/an-introduction-to-futures-and-foresight-2-february-2025
February 19–March 26	Foresight Essentials Training	This online course is designed to help individuals and organizations develop their skills in the art and science of foresight.	Online	https://www.iff.org/trainings/foresight-essentials-feb-19-mar-26-2025/
February 20–21	The 8th International Conference on the Future of Women	This conference attempts to magnify and expedite initiatives focused on fostering a more equitable future for all women. It aims to empower and uplift women worldwide.	Bangkok, Thailand	https://futurewomenconference.com/

Date	Title	Description	Location	Website
February 25–26	Future Festival Miami Innovation Conference	This is a two-day event exploring future trends and innovation through the lens of AI.	Miami, FL, USA	https://www.anticipate.dk/futures-foresight-events/future-festival-miami-2025
February 26	Setting Attainable Decarbonization Goals	This webinar offers actionable insights to balance ambition with practicality, whether you're starting or refining your sustainability efforts.	Online	https://www.fsmgmt.co/foresight-forum
February 27	Earth Tech: 2050 Virtual Pitch Day	This online event addresses some of the world's biggest climate challenges, including in critical areas like carbon capture, energy, agriculture, waste management, mining and minerals.	Online	https://foresightcac.com/event/2025/earth-tech-2050-virtual-pitch-day
March				
March 1	World Futures Day - Young Voices 2025	This will be the eleventh year that futurists and the general public will conduct a 24-hour, round-the-world conversation on the future on March 1 st .	Online	https://www.teachthefuture.org/event-details/world-futures-day-young-voices-2025
March 3–4	Foresight Practitioner Conference 2025	The conference focuses on collaborating and improving forecast practice by showcasing businesses, subject matter experts, and organizations that	Charlotte, NC, USA	https://forecasters.org/events/foresight-practitioner-conference/

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		significantly impact value.		
March 4–18	Three Horizons of AI: A Future-Readiness Course from IFTF	These online sessions will inspect Chat GPT and other generative AI models that will create large-scale disruption across near-term, mid-term, and long-term time horizons.	Online	https://www.iftf.org/trainings/three-horizons-of-ai-training-march-4-11-18/
March 6–7	Strategic Foresight: Futuring for Diplomacy and Organisations	This short course dives into the discipline of future studies and focuses on key methodologies and practices involved in strategic foresight.	Geneva, Switzerland	https://executive.graduateinstitute.ch/programmes/futures-strategic-foresight-diplomacy
March 7–15	SXSW 2025: Forge New Frontiers	SXSW 2025 will place a growing emphasis on foresight in technology, film, television, and music industries.	Austin, TX, USA	https://www.sxsw.com/news/2024/register-for-sxsw-2025-badge-access-savings-and-more/
March 12	Foresight for Beginners in 90 minutes	This is a 90-minute, introductory-level online learning experience that will teach learners how to get started with their own creative foresight.	Online	https://www.iftf.org/trainings/march-2025-fast-futures/
March 13	Strategic Foresight Tools for Startups	Vinny Tafuro has designed this webinar for tech founders and their teams to learn three battle-tested foresight methods.	Online	https://www.eventbrite.com/e/strategic-foresight-tools-for-startups-registration-1117933592469

Date	Title	Description	Location	Website
March 14	Future of Health: AI, Longevity & Mental Wellness	This event takes a deep look into the exciting intersection of AI, longevity, and mental wellness in the future of health.	Hybrid, Paris, France	https://www.eventbrite.com/e/billets-future-of-health-ai-longevity-mental-wellness-1116537225899
March 25–27	IFTF Foresight Essentials for Philanthropy	This training is for learners who work at a grant-funding or grantmaking foundation or organization. Attendees will learn how to build a strategic vision that effectively serves their grantees.	Palo Alto, CA, USA	https://www.iftf.org/trainings/foresight-essentials-for-philanthropy-jan-14-16-2025/
March 26	Successful Sustainability Disclosure: EcoVadis, Supplier Assurance, CDP	This webinar will help attendees improve reporting and position their organization as a sustainability leader.	Online	https://www.fsmgmt.co/foresight-forum
April				
April 2	Unlock The Future Conference 2025	This event offers a platform for property and facilities management leaders to share insights, discuss the big topics, and explore solutions from diverse industries to innovate business directions.	London, UK	https://unlockthefuture.uk/
April 2–5	40th Annual International Conference on Narrative	Florida International University's Science & Fiction Lab and International Society for the Study of Narrative	Miami, FL, USA	https://www.scienceandfiction.fiu.edu/nc-25

Date	Title	Description	Location	Website
		provide attendees with an opportunity to check new possibilities in the realm of science fiction.		
April 3–4	Oceania Futures and Foresight Symposium	The symposium is a community-driven event that invites futurists, foresight practitioners, and those passionate about sustainable futures to come together, share knowledge, and build connections across Oceania.	Brisbane, Australia	https://www.anticipate.dk/futures-foresight-events/oceania-futures-and-foresight-symposium
April 4–5	Eaton Conference on Speculative Fiction	This is a two-day conference on speculative fiction where attendees may share and engage in conversation about their work, foster community and collegiality, and gain conference experience.	Riverside, CA, USA	https://call-for-papers.sas.upenn.edu/cfp/2024/10/28/eaton-conference-on-speculative-fiction
April 14–25	Foundations in Natural Foresight	An interactive online course that empowers learners with the critical skills of strategic foresight and futures thinking for a new era of complexity and change.	Online	https://tfsx.com/learning-events/foundations/
April 23	Automotive & Aftermarket Sustainability Trends: What	In this webinar, the presenters will propose actionable strategies to align with industry	Online	https://www.fsmgmt.co/foresight-forum

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	Suppliers Need to Know	expectations and stay competitive.		
April 23– May 21	Foresight Seminar	This is a 5-day intensive workshop in framework foresight, covering areas such as systems thinking, alternative perspectives, visioning, and planning.	Online	https://dot.egr.uh.edu/programs/professional/fore/seminar
April 28–29	8th Future of Information and Communication Conference	FICC 2025 aims to provide a forum for researchers from both academia and industry to share their latest research contributions and exchange knowledge with the common goal of shaping the future of information and communication.	Berlin, Germany	https://saiconference.com/FICC
April 29	Strategic Foresight for Leaders	An immersive workshop giving participants the foresight skill to thrive into the future, facilitated by futurist Melissa Clark-Reynolds ONZM.	Christchurch, New Zealand	https://www.eventbrite.co.nz/e/strategic-foresight-for-leaders-1-day-workshop-29-april-2025-tickets-1117063630389
April 30– May 2	Future Days 25: Towards Symbiotic Futures	FD25 is a festival dedicated to futures and systemic thinkers, innovators, creatives, purpose-driven organizations, and policymakers, all with a shared vision of shaping the future of urban life	Lisbon, Portugal	https://futuredays.io/

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		and fostering equitable societies.		
May				
May 2	Houston Foresight Spring Gathering 2025	The Houston Foresight Spring Gathering 2025 marks the 50th anniversary of the University of Houston's foresight program.	League City, TX, USA	https://www.houstonforesight.org/save-the-date-spring-gathering-2025/
May 6	Living Future 2025: Accelerating Regenerative Action	This event brings together the brightest minds in sustainability, architecture, design, manufacturing, real estate, and policy.	Portland, OR, USA	https://living-future.org/events/living-future-2025-accelerating-regenerative-action/
May 6–7	EPIC2025	Bringing together education, entertainment and networking, EPIC2025 is a remarkable event of the year for the home services industry.	Orlando, FL, USA	https://epic2025.com/
May 6–8	Hope and resilience 2025	The conference will emphasize the diverse realities of families, children, and young people living across the globe and invites researchers from various fields and disciplines to explore how we can foster well-being, resilience, and hope for the future within families and communities.	Jyväskylä, Finland	https://www.jyu.fi/en/events/hope-and-resilience-2025

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May 8	Future Tense 2025	This is an annual B2B conference focusing on the study of current trends to anticipate future business developments.	Zagreb, Croatia	https://futuretense.eu/
May 8–10	Anticipatory Governance	This conference will explore ways for moving from an essentially reactive bureaucratic organization to an anticipatory one.	Trento, Italy	https://www.trentoinnovation.eu/en/join-us/governance-2025/
May 13	Blockchain Futurist Conference	The 7th Annual Blockchain Futurist Conference is Canada's largest and longest running Web3 event, renowned for its highly immersive and networking-focused experience.	Toronto, ON, Canada	https://www.futuristconference.com/
May 13–15	University:Future Festival	This is the largest event focused on the (digital) future of academic education. Topics for this year's event include AI, future skills, didactics, and strategic processes.	Hybrid / Berlin, Germany	https://festival.hfd.digital/en/
May 15–16	Futures4Europe Foresight Conference	This conference will explore the transformative concept of Future-Oriented Collective Intelligence (FOCI) as a means to address complex and	Vienna, Austria	https://www.futures4europe.eu/post/eye-of-europe-conference-foresight-and-ri-wjyxd

Date	Title	Description	Location	Website
		interconnected challenges.		
May 21–23	Katapult Future Fest 2025	KFF25 is the eight Katapult Future Fest and designed explicitly for impact investors, tech entrepreneurs, and purpose-driven change-makers.	Oslo, Norway	https://katapultfuturefest.com/
May 26–28	Nordic DiGRA 2025 conference Hope	The conference will focus on envisioning the future of game cultures. Presenters will inspect creating positive cultural, societal, and environmental impact as a driving force leading their work.	Turku, Finland	http://nordicdigra2025.org
May 28–29	The Wall Street Journal's Future of Everything Festival	Presenters will be discussing transformative trends, opportunities and challenges across various sectors: business, tech, economics, finance, government, science, sports, style, entertainment and more.	New York City, NY, USA	https://foefestival.wsj.com/event/the-future-of-everything-festival/
June				
June 2–7	SXSW 2025 London	This event promises a dynamic convergence of industries, disciplines, and artforms, offering a platform for innovation, discovery, and	London, UK	

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		collaboration. Attendees can expect keynote talks, artistic interactions, screenings, showcases, fashion activations, and much more.		
June 5	Creative Bureaucracy Festival	The festival focuses on rethinking the principles, processes, and practices of public institutions. It will welcome creative minds, public sector innovators and creative changemakers from all over the world.	Berlin, Germany	https://creativebureaucracy.org/festival
June 10–11	Presidents' Summit 2025: Connecting the Leaders of Tomorrow	The summit provides a vital platform for business leaders and decision-makers from across Europe and beyond to develop their businesses, explore new ideas, and expand their global networks.	Copenhagen, Denmark	https://www.presidents-summit.com/
June 10–12	Futures of Technologies – Mutual Shaping of Socio-Technical Transformations	This conference focuses on the futures of technologies, their development, importance, role and risks as a driver of social change.	Turku, Finland	https://futuresconference2025.com/
June 11–12	NetZero Live 2025 Conference + Exhibition	The event will feature 3-conferences on Industry, CCS and Maritime; creating a	London, UK	https://www.foresight.events/netzero

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		broader pool of attendees to combine sectors individually and collectively.		
June 25–26	Long-Term Strategy Conference	Organized by Framework Consulting Inc., this online event will take a fresh look at sustainable planning in light of futures thinking and foresight.	Online	https://strategyconf.fwconsulting.com/
June 25–27	The Future of Education	The conference brings together teachers, researchers, practitioners and project managers from all over the world to share findings, expertise and experience about innovative teaching and learning methodologies.	Hybrid / Florence, Italy	https://conference.pixel-online.net/FOE/
July				
July 1–3	Teaching and Learning Conference 2025: Future-focused education	This three-day conference, attracting HE practitioners involved in teaching and learning from the UK and overseas, will provide a forum for delegates to share latest research, project outcomes and initiatives that improve teaching and learning practice.	Sheffield, UK	https://www.advance-he.ac.uk/Programmes-events/conferences/Teaching-Learning-2025
July 28–31	11th Annual International	The aim of the symposium is to bring	Athens, Greece	https://www.atiner.gr/foresight

Date	Title	Description	Location	Website
	Symposium on Foresight	together scholars, researchers and students from all areas of Futures Studies and other related disciplines including quantitative and/or qualitative methods and social platforms.		
July 28– August 1	SOIF Summer Retreat in Strategic Foresight	This will be a week-long exploration of strategic foresight and how to transform the future of your organization, community or sector.	London, UK	https://soif.org.uk/foresight-retreat/
August				
August 11– 15	Foresight Seminar	This is a 5-day intensive workshop in framework foresight, covering areas such as systems thinking, alternative perspectives, visioning, and planning.	Houston, TX, USA	https://dot.egr.uh.edu/programs/professional/fore/seminar
September				
September 21	Climate Week NYC 2025	This is the largest annual climate event of its kind, bringing together over 900 events and activities.	Hybrid / New York City, NY, USA	https://www.theclimategroup.org/our-work/events/climate-week-nyc-2025
September 25–27	Speculative Fiction Across Media	This event aims to encourage and foster communication and exchange of ideas among those working in speculative media.	Los Angeles, CA, USA	https://sfamla.org/
September (TBD)	Anticipation 2025	This event will seek to deepen and widen the	Lancaster, UK	https://www.lancaster.ac.uk/social-futures/events/anticipation-conference-2024/

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		exchange of new ideas, and possible future directions seeking reflection and action in the interest of a better collective global future.		
September (TBD)	Asia Pacific Futures Network Annual Conference	As a regional event, the APFN conference intends to take a four-track approach catering for practitioners, academic researchers, government and corporate leaders simultaneously.	TBD	https://www.asiapacificfutures.net/
October				
October 13–16	The 8th international Adaptation Futures Conference (AF2025)	The premier international climate change adaptation conference series enables practitioners, policymakers, researchers, and academics from across the world to gather to network, collaborate, learn, and inspire.	Christchurch, New Zealand	https://adaptationfutures2025.com/
October 13–24	Foundations in Natural Foresight	An interactive online course that empowers learners with the critical skills of strategic foresight and futures thinking for a new era of complexity and change.	Online	https://tfsx.com/schedule/foundations-global-october-13-15-17-20-22-24-2025/

Date	Title	Description	Location	Website
October 22–24	4th World Conference on Climate Change & Sustainability	The conference’s theme is “Addressing Global Climate Change for a Sustainable Future” to accelerate collaboration and integrate climate action into global pandemic recovery.	Milan, Italy	https://climateweek.thepeopleevents.com/
October 25–26	Fixing the Future	Over two packed days, this event will gather the top 25 future-shaping projects from around the globe, showcasing innovative solutions in areas such as AI technologies, farming innovation, drought mitigation, and creative recycling.	Barcelona, Spain	https://fixingthefuture.atlasofthefuture.org/en/
October 29–31	WFSF Conference	World Futures Studies Federation (WFSF) has been holding annual conferences around the globe for 50 years in diverse places. This year, WFSF members will gather in Cape Town to discuss a number of future-focused topics.	Cape Town, South Africa	https://wfsf.org/wfsf-world-regional-conferences/
November				
November 25–27	Anticipate London	Anticipate London, emerging from the fusion of IFSEC, FIREX, Safety & Health Expo, and the Facilities Show, is the	London, UK	https://www.anticipate-event.com/london/en/home.html

Date	Title	Description	Location	Website
		leading event for property and people professionals aiming to thrive amidst an uncertain future.		
November (TBD)	Dubai Future Foundation	This event will be likely the biggest gathering of futurists organized by Dubai Future Foundation.	Dubai, UAE	https://www.dubaifuture.ae/events
December				
December 2	13th Global Dialogue Platform on anticipatory humanitarian action	Participants share and exchange knowledge, best practices and lessons learned to ensure there is a fundamental change within the humanitarian system: from reaction to anticipation.	Hybrid / Berlin, Germany	https://www.anticipation-hub.org/events/13th-global-dialogue-platform-on-anticipatory-humanitarian-action-10th-anniversary-edition

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Nuts About
Leadership

A Journal of Leadership and Futures Studies

Nuts About Leadership is an online peer-reviewed journal dedicated to advancing the fields of leadership and futures studies. It explores cutting-edge theories, methodologies, and practices in leadership development and future-oriented strategies.

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